

KHOJA MUHAMMAD PORSO – A GREAT REPRESENTATIVE OF THE KHOJAGON-NAQSHBANDIYA SECT

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Studying the scientific heritage and views of Muhammad bin Muhammad bin Mahmud al-Hafizi al-Bukhari, one of the theorists of Sufism at the end of the 14th century, a major representative of the Khojagon-Naqshbandi sect, known as Khoja Muhammad Porso It allows us to study more deeply the teachings of Sufism, which arose in the heart of Sufism, and the original content of the philosophy of mysticism, which has been formed in the framework of Sufism for more than a thousand years.

In this part of our project "Great figures of our spirituality" we talk about Muhammad bin Mahmud al-Hafizi al-Bukhari. Born in Bukhara in 1345, Khwaja Muhammad Porso studied in the madrasas here, studied the Holy Qur'an and hadith sciences in depth, and became one of the leading scholars of his time. After Naqshband, Bahauddin became famous as the greatest representative and propagator of the Naqshbandi movement in the Islamic world.

Khoja Muhammad Porso communicated with Khalil Sultan, ruler of Mowarounnahr, corresponded with Shahrukh Mirza on various issues. Mirza took part in scientific debates in the palace of Ulugbek (Samarkand and Bukhara).

Hazrat Bahauddin Naqshband gave the honorific title "Porso" (pious, pious) to Khwaja Muhammad. Khwaja Muhammad Porso's relationship with Bahauddin Naqshband is perfectly described in the work entitled "Maqamoti Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband" by Muhammad Baqir, who lived in this period. According to the book "Tuhfat uz-zairin", Khwaja Muhammad Porso Bahauddin was the second caliph of Naqshband. The great mystic had high hopes for this student and paid special attention to his education. In Fakhruddin Ali Safi's work "Rashahot", the following story of Khoja Muhammad Porso is given: "On the way to Hijaz, Khojai Buzrug (Bahouddin) fell ill and made a will. At the same time, in the presence of his friends, he turned to this assembly and said: "Whatever happened to this weak one from the caliphs of the House of Hojagons and whatever he found on this way, I have handed over to you all these deposits. Send all of these deposits to the people of Haq subhonahu." When we returned from the trip to the Hijaz, in the presence of friends, they said: "Whatever we have, you have taken everything." At the end of their lives, they said: "The reason for our existence was the appearance of Muhammad (Porso)."

Khwaja Ali Domod, one of his close relatives, describes the fact that Bahauddin Naqshband appointed Khwaja Muhammad Porso in his place before his death: "During his last illness, Hazrat Khwaja Bahavuddin ordered to dig the grave where his body is now lying." After digging the grave, I came to them. The thought crossed my mind that who are they appointing to the work of irshad after them. They suddenly turned to me and said: "What I said on the way to Hejaz is true, whoever dreams of us, let him look at Khoja Muhammad Porso."

These examples are evidence of the great respect and faith of Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband towards his student. Khoja Muhammad Porso, like his mentor, was concerned about the condition of the believers and interfered in the affairs of the kings. At the beginning of a story presented in "Rashahot" the strong power of karamat in Khwaja Muhammad Porso is

evidenced, then it is shown that the scholars of the time and the king were concerned about the purity of science.

According to Ali Safi, the author of "Rashahot", Khoja Muhammad Porso had a strong charisma, but he tried to hide it as much as possible. However, he was forced to reveal it only when it was absolutely necessary. The details of one such event are as follows: "The leader of hadith scholars, Sheikh Shamsuddin Muhammad ibn Muhammad al-Jazari, peace be upon him, came to Samarkand during the time of Mirza Ulugbek. Some selfish people say: "Hazrat Khoja Muhammad Porso narrates a lot of hadiths in Bukhara, and no one knows whether their asnads are correct or incorrect." "It wouldn't be bad if Hazrat Sheikh checked it," he said. His Highness Sheikh came to the bottom of this matter. They persuaded Mirza Ulugbek to this, sent people to Bukhara and asked Hazrat Khoja (Muhammad Porso) to come to Samarkand. Thus, the sheikh organized a big meeting together with Khoja Isomiddin, the sheikhulislam of Samarkand, and the greatest scholars. Khoja Muhammad also arrived at the meeting. The sheikh asked him to recite a hadith along with his asnadi. When Khwaja Muhammad said, the sheikh said: "There is no doubt about the authenticity of this hadith, but its source is not known to us." The envious were happy at this word and winked at each other. Khwaja Muhammad also narrated the second source of this hadith. The Sheikh repeated his above statement. They understood that no matter how many documents Khwaja Muhammad says, his words will not be accepted here. Then they discussed for a moment, and after a little silence, they looked at the Shaykh and said: "Do you recognize such and such a hadith book and do you consider its asnads to be authoritative?" Shaykh: "Yes, all the asnads in that book are worthy of attention and trust." "None of the scholars of Hadith doubt it, if the asnads you mentioned are from this book, then we have no objection."

Hazrat Khwaja (Muhammad Porso) looked at Khwaja Isomiddin and said: "In your library, there is a book with such and such volume on such and such a shelf, under such and such a book, in which the asnad we mentioned is detailed on such and such a page. Please send one of your employees to bring it quickly." Khoja Isomiddin hesitated whether this document was there or not. And the people in the meeting were lost in thought. It was known to everyone that Hazrat Khoja was not in this private library. Thus, Khoja Isomiddin immediately sent one of his relatives to his house and ordered him to bring the said things if they were there. He found a book and a document according to the mentioned signs and brought it to the meeting. The said hadith was present on the same page with those asnads without any difference. Hearing this, voices of surprise rose from the people of the assembly. The sheikh and other scholars were surprised. Especially, Khwaja Isomiddin's surprise was greater than that of others, because he was not aware of the existence of this documental book in his house. Hearing this story, Mirza Ulug'bek was embarrassed to call Hazrat Khoja. This blessing that happened to Hazrat Khwaja strengthened people's beliefs about them.

"Rashahot" reports that Khoja Muhammad Porso was involved in the political events of that time. Khalil Mirza, the son of Amir Temur's son Muhammad Jahangir, as well as Shahrukh Mirza, the king of Khurasan, were well aware of his activities. According to sources, Porso corresponded with Shahrukh Mirza on various issues. The following works of Khoja Muhammad Porso are stored in the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni, FA of Uzbekistan:

1. "Risolai Qudsiya" ("A treatise on the holy words of Khwaja Bahauddin").

2. "Az anfozi qudsiyai mashoyihi tariqat" ("From the holy words of the masters of the tariqat").
3. "Treatise on faith".
4. "Tahqiqat" ("Treatise on Sufism Istilah").
5. "Tafsiri Qur'an" ("Tafsir Qur'an").
6. "Al-hadith ul-arba'una" ("Forty hadiths").
7. "Risola dar odobi murid" ("Treatise about murid manners").
8. "Risolai kashfiya" ("Treatise on Karomat").
9. "Risalai mahbubiya" ("Treatise about friendship").
10. "Sharhi "Fiqhi Kaidaniy" ("Commentary of the work "Fiqhi Kaidaniy").
11. "Fasl ul-hitab bi-vusuli-ahbab" ("The book that separates white from black in reaching the friendship of friends").
12. "A brief history of Mecca" ("A brief history of the city of Mecca").
13. "Fusuli sitta" ("Six seasons").
14. "Letter of Khwaja Muhammad Porso and Mawlana Zainuddin" ("Letter of Khwaja Muhammad Porso to Mawlana Zainuddin").
15. "Maqamoti Khwaja Alauddin Attar" ("Maqamoti Alauddin Attar").
16. "Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband Authority" ("Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband Authority").
17. "Muqaddima li-jami' ul-kalim" ("Preface to the book "Jami' ul-kalim").
18. "Haftodu du firqa" ("Seventy two sects").

Muhammad Porso's "Risolai Qudsiya" is a commentary on the Qudsi words of Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband. These words were heard from Bahauddin Naqshband's own mouth, and Muhammad Porso compiled them. He himself says about this: "These words are just a drop of the words that came out of (their) blessed mouths, and this weak servant... used to pen some of these holy words as a blessing and a guide for devotion and will." In this work, Muhammad Porso not only quotes the sacred words of his teacher, but also interprets them. The work is extremely valuable as it reveals the life, services and spiritual world of Bahauddin Naqshband and contains in-depth information about the foundations of the Naqshbandiyya leech.

The work of Muhammad Porso, dedicated to issues of Sharia and Tariqat, which brought him great fame, is called "Fasl un-hitab bi-vusuli-l-ahbob" ("The book that separates white from black in reaching the friendship of friends"). This large book was used as a guide among Islamic scholars. The work has been published several times. If there is any dispute about the Sharia, tariqat and sects, they refer to "Fasl un-Khitob" and see Porso's opinion as a document and rely on it. The work deals with 494 issues, all of which are considered controversial in Islam, and Porso solves these issues based on various works.

Khoja Muhammad Porso performed Hajj twice. First, Bahauddin went with Naqshband, then in 1419 he went from Bukhara through Termiz, Balkh and Herat to Nishapur, and from there to Medina. After performing Hajj, he fell ill and died in Medina in 1419 at the age of 72. He was buried next to the tomb of Amir al-mo'minin Abbas.

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